

Oil Price Volatility and Macroeconomic Factors Influence Stock Market Return: A Study In Malaysia

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Abstract:

The prime objective of this study is to analysis the impact of crude oil prices and macroeconomic variables on the stock market of Malaysia .For this purpose we have taken the data from 1981-2011 and applied the Johnson co integration, ECM and unit root test. Our results are showing that there is significant association between crude oil prices, macroeconomic variables on the stock market of Malaysia .Hence, final analysis is showing that the major responsible bank of Malaysia should control the dwindling position on interest rate and focus on the transparency system for developing the confidence level of all investors.

Keywords: *crude oil,ECM, unit root test, cointegration, central bank*

Introduction;

From the 2008, the degree of association between crude oil prices and macroeconomic variables are known as the hot issue for the entire economist. Our study is trying to expose that sharp changes in the prices of crude oil has huge impact on the economics of the country. From the last few decades the plausible expiations about the association between oil prices and mare comic variables have occupied the minds of researchers'.According to Hamilton(2003), there were huge pioneering studies about the impact of the crude oil on the macroeconomic variables and this study is showing that oil price episode impact on the recession. The supply side effect is showing that crude oil is basic tool for the production.

According to economic theory stock prices is best predictor about the firm s earning. The fundamental value of the firm s prices can be calculated by the present values .Hence, the profit s earning is the part of investment,GDP and investment.Therefore,it is not wrong that economic activities can be calculated by the stock prices.

The oil boom had worst impact on the economic development of all the contries.Oil suddenly had very huge impact on the exports of the countries and exports of all the countries are consider crucial role for the progress. In the 1978 the crude oil shortage was start and in these years, it is seen that oil crisis had worst impact on the import, export and some other macroeconomic variables. In 1995, there were worst currencydevaluation and inflation in the world. Between 1998 and 2011 there were moderate inflation rate are seen.However,at the September 2012 ,the rate of inflation were seen at 11.3%.Currently,all over the world the banking system are being making polices about the inflation rate. Central bank of Malaysia are also doing working about the policies, how can control the devaluation of currency. In 2008 the global recession were occurred .During this time sophisticated stock market was badly affected and all over the world were faced the oil crisis. It is very difficult task to analysis the impact of crude oil on the stock market of Malaysia.

Objectives:

- Impact of macroeconomic variables on the stock return ofMalaysia.
- Impact of crude oil on the performance of Malaysia s economy.
- All the variables are long run relationship or short run relationship between the variables.

Problem statement:

From the last few decades impact of crude oil on the economy of Malaysia.

Figure no 1:

Followers of the oil market will be familiar with the recent evolution of oil supply and price:

Figure no 2: Fuel consumption by sector

Literature review:

Ahhmed ,Analyzed the impact of macroeconomic variables and crude oil on the development of Nigera.For this purpose, they taken the data from years 1998-2008 and applied the VAR model .the results are showing that there is positive

association between macroeconomic variables, crude oil and stock market of Nigeria .They suggested that inflation has influenced on the progress of stock exchange, therefore, government should focus on the polices about the increasing inflation rate [1].

Alile, Observed the impact of macroeconomic variables and crude oil on the development of Pakistan. For this purpose, they taken the data from years 1991-2009 and applied the ECM model .the results are showing that there is positive association between macroeconomic variables, crude oil and stock market of Pakistan .They suggested that exchange rate has influenced on the progress of stock exchange, therefore, government should focus on the polices about the increasing inflation rate[2].

Ayadi et al , Viewed the impact of macroeconomic variables and crude oil on the development of India. For this purpose, they taken the data from years 1999-2012 and applied the multiregression model .The results are showing that there is positive association between macroeconomic variables, crude oil and stock market of India .They suggested that oil prices has influenced on the progress of stock exchange, therefore, government should focus on the polices about the increasing inflation rate[3].

Gunu Umar ,Examined the impact of macroeconomic variables and crude oil on the development of USA .For this purpose, they taken the data from years 1990-2010 and applied the unit root model .the results are showing that there is positive association between macroeconomic variables, crude oil and stock market of USA .They suggested that inflation has influenced on the progress of stock exchange, therefore, government should focus on the polices about the increasing inflation rate [4].

Hamilton J. D ,Viewed the impact of macroeconomic variables and crude oil on the development of UK .For this purpose, they taken the data from years 1986-2009 and applied the OLS model .the results are showing that there is positive association between macroeconomic variables, crude oil and stock market of UK .They suggested that inflation has influenced on the progress of stock exchange, therefore, government should focus on the polices about the increasing inflation rate [5].

Hamilton, James D., Observed the impact of macroeconomic variables and crude oil on the development of France .For this purpose, they taken the data from years 1991-2009 and applied the VAR model .the results are showing that there is positive association between macroeconomic variables, crude oil and stock market of France .They suggested that inflation has influenced on the progress of stock exchange, therefore, government should focus on the polices about the increasing inflation rate [6].

Hooker M., viewed the impact of macroeconomic variables and crude oil on the development of china .For this purpose, they taken the data from years 1996-2006 and applied the ECM model .the results are showing that there is positive association between macroeconomic variables, crude oil and stock market of china .They suggested that inflation has influenced on the progress of stock exchange, therefore, government should focus on the polices about the increasing inflation rate [7].

Jin ,Analyzed the impact of macroeconomic variables and crude oil on the development of Japan .For this purpose, they taken the data from years 1998-2008 and applied the OLS model .the results are showing that there is positive association between macroeconomic variables, crude oil and stock market of Japan .They suggested that inflation has influenced on the progress of stock exchange, therefore, government should focus on the polices about the increasing inflation rate [8].

Hamilton J. D ,Analyzed the impact of macroeconomic variables and crude oil on the development of Malaysia .For this purpose, they taken the data from years 1976-2007 and applied the VAR model .the results are showing that there is positive association between macroeconomic variables, crude oil and stock market of Malaysia .They suggested that inflation has influenced on the progress of stock exchange, therefore, government should focus on the polices about the increasing inflation rate [9].

Hamilton, James D., Analyzed the impact of macroeconomic variables and crude oil on the development of Jordan .For this purpose, they taken the data from years 1992-2002 and applied the linear model .the results are showing that there is positive association between macroeconomic variables, crude oil and stock market of Jordan .They suggested that inflation has influenced on the progress of stock exchange, therefore, government should focus on the polices about the increasing inflation rate [10].

Hooker M. ,Analyzed the impact of macroeconomic variables and crude oil on the development of Amman .For this purpose, they taken the data from years 1993-2003 and applied the VECMmodel .The results are showing that there is positive association between macroeconomic variables, crude oil and stock market of Amman .They suggested that inflation has influenced on the progress of stock exchange, therefore, government should focus on the polices about the increasing inflation rate [11].

Gaps in literature review:

- 1) We have sought out impact of long run association of macroeconomic variables on the Malaysia stock exchange.
- 2) During financial crisis what were the impact of crude oil on the rate on inflation
- 3) In which years the rate of inflation was more and how all the stock market were affected due to recession.

Theoretical framework:

Figure no 3:

Methodology:(wozip)

In this paper,we have followed the approach of Gunu (2010) paper title: impact of oil prices on the stock exchange of Malaysia: According to his approach there is significant association between oil prices and stock market of Malaysia .Firstly,we have taken the data from 1981-2011.we have applied the co integration ,unit root and ECM model for the proper results our main variables are given below.

$$GDP = b_0 + b_1oil_price01(-1) + b_2sp(-1) + b_3GDP(-2) + b_4oil_price01(-2) + b_5sp(-2).$$

From the above, our model is specified as:

$$RGDP = f(RSP, ROP, INT, RER)$$

Where RGDP = Growth rate of Gross Domestic Product

RSP = Growth rate of stock price indexed by GDP

ROP = Growth rate of oil price indexed by GDP

INT = Interest rate

RER = Real exchange rate

The structural form is

$$RGDP = a_0 + a_1RSP + a_2ROP + a_3INT + a_4RER + u$$

Empirical results:

first, we have applied the OLS method and results of other tests are given below.

Table 1:

Ordinary Least Square				
Dependent Variable: RGDP				
Method: Least Squares				
Sample(adjusted): 1986 2011				
Included observations: 27 after adjusting endpoints				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.010488	0.010858	0.965722	0.3453
ROP	-0.002503	0.001084	-2.310661	0.0312
RSP	19.92831	0.014833	1343.614	0
INT	-0.000932	0.000559	-1.668258	0.1102
EXR	0.000296	6.12E-07	4.815722	0.0002
R-squared	0.999992	Mean dependent var	4.811537	
Adjusted R-squared	0.999988	S.D. dependent var	3.466677	
S.E. of regression	0.0113101	Akaike info criterion	-5.955301	
Sum squared resid	0.002687	Schwarz criterion	-5.713359	
Log likelihood	82.41891	F-statistic	587237.6	
Durbin-Watson stat	1.300027	Prob(F-statistic)	0	
RGDP = a ₀ + a ₁ ROP + a ₂ SP + a ₃ INT + a ₄ EXR + u				
RGDP = 0.010488 - 0.002503ROP + 19.92831RSP - 0.000932INT + 0.000296EXR				
R-squared = 0.998	Durbin Watson = 1.4			

Above model is showing that there is positive association between RGDP and SP and negative association between ROP and INT .This implication is the showing that 1% increase in RSP will bring increase about 19.8% and 0.000296b% and 0.00094 % respectively .the value of R square is showing the RGDP tune to 98% .The value of Durbin waston 1.4 explains that there is positive correlation between the variables.

Table 2

Stationarity Test (Unit Root)			
Variable	ADF - Statistics	Critical Value	Order of integration
RGDP	-11.37221	1% = -3.6753*	I(0)
	5% = -2.9666		
	10% = -2.6221		
ROP	-56.38464	1% = -3.6753	I(0)
		5% = -2.9666	Stationary at level
		10% = -2.6221	
RSP	-2.740028	10% = -2.6349	I(0)
			Stationary at level
INT	-2.038215	5% = -1.953859	I(1)
		10% = -1.609572	Stationary at first difference
EXR	-3.598318	5% = -2.9706	I(1)
	10% = -2.6243		Stationary at first difference

The results of ADF unit root is showing that all the variables are stationary at level 1 and significant at 5 and 10 % respectively .these results are showing that RGDP<ROP and RSP are all stationary .All the variables are integrated at the order of 1.

Table no 3:

Cointegration Test				
Johansen Cointegrating Test.				
Eigen Value	Likelihood	5 percent	1 percent	Hypothesized
	Ratio	Critical Value	Critical Value	No of CE(s)
0.931046	83.58756	29.69	35.66	None **
0.483172	16.73005	15.42	20.05	At most 1*
0.009117	0.228941	3.77	6.66	At most 2

*(**) denotes rejection of the hypothesis at 5%(1%) significance level.

The value of table no 2 Eigen statistics shows that there are cointegration between the variables. It shows that there is long run relationship between the variables.

$$RGDP = 0.104114 - 0.076848ROP + 20.01231RSP$$

Table no 4:

Dependent Variable: RGDP
 Method: Least Squares
 Sample (adjusted): 1987 2010
 Included observations: 24 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.014746	0.042885	-0.343841	0.7362
RGDP(-1)	2.101727	4.774979	0.440155	0.6666
ROP	0.006851	0.016249	0.421551	0.6799
RSP	19.91754	0.015926	1250.716	0
RSP(-1)	-41.89517	95.19541	-0.440097	0.6667
EXR	2.46E-06	0.000166	0.148885	0.8839
EXR(-1)	-0.000317	0.001498	-0.210467	0.8364
INT	-0.000908	0.000801	-1.133788	0.2758
INT(-1)	0.002263	0.004659	0.485557	0.6349
ECM	-1.810844	4.701832	-0.385137	0.7058
R-squared	0.999995	Mean dependent var	4.7126	
Adjusted R-squared	0.999991	S.D. dependent var	3.444606	
S.E. of regression	0.010724	Akaike info criterion	-5.938522	
Sum squared resid	0.001611	Schwarz criterion	-5.447466	
Log likelihood	81.26107	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-5.808497	
F-statistic	263671.8	Durbin-Watson stat	2.096857	
Prob(F-statistic)	0			

The values of ROP,INT and RSP are showing that there is short run association between the variables and all are significant. There is not short run relationship between exchange rate and other variables. For example, values are proving that 1 % increase in ROP, and RSP will increase the RGDP while, 1 % increase in the inflation will decrease the growth rate.

In the long run, the ECM coefficient of -1.812(negative) and RGDP(-2) coefficient of 2.101727(positive) are significant, implying that a long run relationship exist among the variables (lag 1) at equilibrium.

The model;

$$RGDP = a_0 + a_1RGDP(-1) + a_2ROP + a_3RSP + a_4RSP(-1) + a_5EXR + a_6EXR(-1) + a_7INT + a_8INT(-2) + a_9ECM$$

$$RGDP = -0.014746 + 2.101727RGDP(-1) + 0.006860ROP + 19.91754RSP - 41.89517RSP(-1) + 2.47E-05EXR - 0.000317EXR(-1) - 0.000908INT + 0.002272INT(-1) - 1.810743ECM$$

Conclusion and recommendation:

Our empirical results are showing that GDP is significant affected by the EXP<ROP and RSP. Here, it is interesting to know that RSP is larger than other variables and it has the crucial role for the economic development. While, other variables like RSP and ROP are concerned by the interest rate and exchange rate. Finally, it is proved that central bank of Malaysia is steadily manage the nature of interest rate. Interest rate is the single variables through which investors can take proper decision about the further and existing investment. Second way to boost the confidence on investors is with the help of CBN, which can ensure the

Accountability of stock exchange .Third ,government should focus on the oil crisis .this can be possible with the adequate policies.

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